

INTRODUCTION

Applied plasma research involves several disciplines such as physics, medicine and biology to solve application-oriented problems, often generating large heterogeneous data sets. One application field is plasma medicine, where bioimaging plays a key role. Similar to most imaging workflows, metadata from several sections of the experiment are required. Therefore, the metadata schema Plasma-MDS [1] is adapted to collect plasma-related metadata, such as information on the plasma species having an impact on the treated samples. The Recommended Metadata for Biological Images (REMBI) standard is used for the biological metadata. These metadata must be combined for a comprehensive description of the microscopy images. However, this requires the implementation and **use of research data management (RDM)** solutions to consider the influence of plasma parameters, treatment procedures and the effects on the treated targets. To achieve this, one of the application-specific developments within the NFDI4BIOIMAGE consortium is presented.

METADATA COLLECTION IN THE LAB (A)

- **Domain specific metadata schemas** are used to collect structured metadata
- RDM tool used to collect the laboratory specific metadata is **Adamant** [2]
- Adamant presents JSON schemas in HTML forms and enables metadata validation
- Metadata for the technical description of microscopes are collected by **Micro Meta App** [3]
- **Laboratory** (except biological metadata for wells) and **microscopy metadata** are stored in **JSON format**
- **Biological metadata** (based on REMBI) are collected in **Excel sheets**
- **Image acquisition metadata** are collected and automatically attached in **proprietary image format**

METADATA STORAGE IN eLabFTW (B)

- **Electronic laboratory notebook eLabFTW** [4] is utilized for describing the experiments
- **Collected metadata** from each experiment are **stored and organized in eLabFTW**
- eLabFTW provides organizational functions for experiments and resources by categories, tags and clear allocations to different groups and teams
- **Coherent experiments and resources can be linked to provide provenance**
- **eLabFTW allows users to timestamp experiments** and their attachments using the Bloxberg blockchain, **making them tamper-proof**

METADATA LINKING IN OMERO (C)

- Images from bioimaging experiments are not stored in eLabFTW as the **image database OMERO** [5] is used for this purpose
- OMERO is a platform for managing, storing and sharing microscopy images
- OMERO provides **image annotation** on different hierarchical orders by key-value pairs
- Plasma research imaging experiments are set up in 96 well plates, which fit OMERO's hierarchical structure “Screens”
- Screens consist of plates, which are organized in wells
- **Annotation is automatized** via Python code (e.g. by Jupyter notebooks)
- **Metadata for annotation are extracted from eLabFTW**
- Only necessary metadata for each substructure are displayed

References:

[1] S. Franke et al. *Scientific Data*, 2020, DOI: 10.1038/s41597-020-00771-0
 [2] I. Chaerony Siffa et al. *F1000Research*, 2022, DOI: 10.12688/f1000research.110875.2
 [3] A. Rigano, et al. *Nature Methods*, 2021, DOI: 10.1038/s41592-021-01315-z
 [4] N. CARPi et al. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 2017, DOI: 10.21105/joss.00146
 [5] C. Allan et al. *Nature Methods*, 2012, DOI: 10.1038/nmeth.1896

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